
Political Communications for President and Vice President in The Regency of Sambas Indonesia

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ABSTRACT : *Political communication is a process of delivering moral messages in politics in the form of visions and missions through work programs and political issues from presidential and vice-presidential candidates and legislative candidates as communicators to the public as voters or communicants through certain media to give a heart effect. They are interested in choosing. This study aims to analyze how the success of the presidential and vice-presidential candidates and the success team of the political party who are legislative candidates in persuading voters use a grounded research approach in qualitative studies. This study found that the main policy strategy to achieve that is with optimize the potential of existing natural and human resources as well as by taking advantage of existing opportunities and overcoming challenges by overcoming the problems faced.*

KEYWORDS - *political communication, presidential and vice-presidential candidates*

I.INTRODUCTION

Interactions and individuals and constructions of reality have evolved into personal media platforms about exposure to campaign rhetoric[1]. Furthermore, the presentation of campaign rhetoric is a form of political communication, among others, for candidates for President and Vice President.

Furthermore, the success team from political parties as Legislative Candidates in delivering the vision and mission through future work programs and political issues to be conveyed[2]. Thus, building political communication is a tool for the president and vice president candidates and the success team. Therefore, according to the author, political communication is a process of delivering moral messages in politics through visions and missions through work programs and political issues from presidential and vice-presidential candidates and legislative candidates as communicators to the public voters or communicants. Through certain media to give the effect that their hearts are interested in choosing.

Choose one of the candidate pairs in the Presidential election and Legislative election for national leadership from the support of local communities in border areas. Therefore, every candidate for the presidential and presidential elections must strive hard to win the constituents' hearts to vote. It should also be remembered, according to the author, that partisanship can often occur in political communication, meaning that there is a successful team as well as Legislative candidates from supporters of the Presidential and Vice-Presidential candidates, there is a tendency to overestimate the positions and actions of groups than other candidates. Partisanship can tend to result in inaccuracies of facts. Political communication also encourages the development of information and political understanding as political participation.

Participants can see the times when the candidate positioned his partner better and was committed to the welfare of the people than the other candidate pairs. Every candidate for the presidential and legislative pairs

needs the media as a means of political messages. The media has a strategic place in the study of political communication. Moreover, now the world is in the transition from the industrial era to the information age. Information becomes a marketable commodity like selling work programs, political issues. Every work program and political issue that is informed can genuinely be accounted for. Candidates as presidential and legislative pairs must be sensitive to the environment and issues in border communities.

The essence of democracy is the involvement of the people in the formation and administration of government through participation, representation, and supervision. The government can also be organized in service to the community in the concept of democracy [3]. As a result, it is linked to presidential and parliamentary elections as the primary ways of exercising sovereignty through voting and presidential and parliamentary elections, respectively. Other elements of the rule of law are implemented through presidential and parliamentary elections, such as preserving human rights, including the right to vote and be elected, and the manifestation of equality before the law and governance. According to the author that the Presidential election and legislative election are carried out directly, simultaneously in which there are two positions, namely as a mechanism for transferring power from the people to the state, namely choosing the position of President for five years and as a legitimizer for the legitimate government. As well as electing the legislature for the next five-year term.

Because it is carried out simultaneously and directly, the people can determine their choice of pairs of presidential candidates and legislative candidates who can be trusted to govern for the next five years as President and Vice President and Legislature. In developed countries, political parties mobilize their political marketing skills to win as many constituents as possible. Several intriguing issue strategies and techniques previously only used commercially have now been grafted into political practice.

The more sophisticated the marketing strategies and techniques applied in political life, the more open the chances of winning are. In line with the opinion above, the efforts of the candidate pairs, the victorious team, and the legislative candidates who implement the issue as a political practice strategy that successfully implements infrastructure development at the border are capital for political marketing. All tactics are used to get high ratings, and people vote for them in the voting booths. Furthermore, when considering how people respond to political communication, the emotional component of information processing becomes critical (Marcus, Neuman, & MacKuen, 2002; Neuman, Marcus, Crigler, & Mackuen, 2009).

Furthermore, border development is a focal point for political marketing methods to improve relationships between candidates and voters. Voters are parties that must be comprehended, comprehended, and a solution found to every problem in the border zone. Voters are the topic of political marketing, not the object of manipulation and exploitation. Based on this, there is political communication on success as political capital in the presidential and legislative elections by analyzing the vision and mission of the work program for the next five years, namely 2019—2024 in local politics in Sambas Regency. In this study, how the success of the presidential and vice-presidential candidate pairs and the Success Team from political parties that are legislative candidates to persuade voters.

II.METHOD

This research using a grounded research approach in qualitative studies. The choice of this approach is intended to examine social phenomena and realities by describing the success of border development as political capital. The presidential election of ingkamben in Sambas Regency in 2019. Political parties as to the subject of supporting candidates for President and Vice President and Legislative candidates simultaneously to be carried out research this year. 2019 in Sambas Regency in a span of 5 (five) months, May to September 2019. In data collection techniques, of course, obtained through observation, interviews, and distributing questionnaires as comparisons in the field in 19 (nineteen) Subdistricts in Sambas Regency, as well as documentation.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In-depth analysis and comprehensively affect the image of voters in the presidential election and legislative elections. There are differences in vote acquisition. In delivering the work program of each campaign

through television, radio, in the field, and at home, continuously according to the specified schedule. Significant influence on political issues about explaining the work program of each Presidential and Vice-Presidential Candidate and Legislative candidate. However, the author focuses first on the presidential election debate witnessed by the Indonesian people and, more specifically, the border community of Sambas Regency. So that 19 can be analyzed from several debates through live television media witnessed throughout Indonesia and specifically in 19 (nineteen) sub-districts in Sambas Regency.

Of course, the 5 (five) direct debates greatly affected the electability of the two presidential and vice-presidential candidates. Regarding the mission and vision of the five-year government's work program, the two pairs of candidates for President and Vice President showed that both candidates were aware of the various problems they faced. However, what is missing from the vision and mission of the two candidates is a way of thinking economically. Government budgets and capacities are limited and, at the same time, many political challenges. Many aspects of the economy need to be improved, and many policies need to be made to encourage higher and equitable economic growth while maintaining environmental conditions. Supposedly, the vision and mission contain a priority scale, such as (i) what sectoral reforms will be carried out first and the reasons and (ii) how much will pay a program/policy cost and its potential benefits. Without this discussion, the vision and mission will only become a 'shopping list' or a 'wish list,' which is not very meaningful.

In line with the Presidential and Vice-Presidential debate analysis results above, the Research Team obtained information from interviews with several supporting political parties in Sambas Regency. That is, as a direct interview was conducted with the management of the PDIP Chairman of Sambas Regency with the initials RD who said that:

"The debate results between the President and the Vice President, which were broadcast live by several television stations, were very influential for voters in 19 (nineteen) sub-districts in Sambas Regency. Moreover, what is offered is the vision, mission, and of course, a work program. For a presidential candidate like Jokowi, this is a flashback evaluation of what has been done during his administration's 4 (four) years. While Pak Prabowo has no experience as President, I think this is a plus for fracture candidates. So I believe that Mr. Jokowi will be able to maintain the position of President in the eyes of the people in Sambas Regency who have been exposed to the information on the television communication media."

Similarly, the results of an interview with the Chairman of the Golkar Political Party with the initials AR in Sambas Regency said that:

"The debate round after round of the presidential candidates is eagerly awaited by all Indonesian people, including the voters in Sambas Regency. I am part of the Jokowi O1 Success team. Our candidate will win again in this presidential election because he has 4 (four) years of experience in governing. The successes that have been achieved will be assessed directly by the people in Sambas Regency. The people of Sambas Regency are very open with all information about the presidential candidate debate which describes the vision and mission through the work program for the next 5 (five) years of his government".

Of the two Success Teams for President O1 Jokowi, who is also the Chairman of the Sambas Regency Political Party, they are very sure that the people will still choose to continue the government for the second time. Although, of course, it still has limitations in its coverage to all regions in Indonesia. Especially for Sambas Regency, development has been proven during its 4 (four) years of administration by constructing road infrastructure that connects the Regency City to the Aruk and Paloh borders. Although the construction for the Paloh border has not been completed, the construction for the Aruk Sajingan border has been completed. In the Presidential and Vice-Presidential Elections in Sambas Regency in each electoral district in 19 (nineteen) sub-districts, the number of abstentions is very high in terms of community participation.

The presidential election, which the people of Sambas Regency dominantly choose, is the vision and mission factor that is packaged in the work program of the President and Vice President, which is more dominant than the influence of political figures and parties as supporters. This is one of the essential milestones that represent the sovereignty of the people, so it can be said that there is no democracy without providing the opportunity for general elections to be held systematically and periodically. Therefore, the presidential election in Sambas Regency on April 17, 2019, can also be classified as the most crucial element in the democratic system. If a country has carried out the presidential election process properly, transparently, fairly, regularly, and continuously,

The results of an interview with a Community Leader of Sambas Regency, April 14, 2019, with the initials HS, said that the presidential election and legislative elections were caused by several things as follows:

"According to him, the success or failure of a presidential election and a legislative election which is a natural manifestation of people's sovereignty is seen from the work program, the figure factor, while for the legislative election for political parties, the candidates are high-influenced, as well as the directives that the community follows and respects. It is fundamental in the democratic process if the people only get directions without having the freedom to choose. It has a significant meaning in moving the wheels and the democratic system to elect the President and Vice President and legislative elections without going through directives. If the people of Sambas Regency in my area have a high level of participation, then the political development process will run well. It will also be significant for the development of the nation and state in this region. On the other hand, political participation will also be meaningless and meaningless if it does not meet the requirements in terms of qualitative and quantitative terms. Therefore, the level of public political participation in the presidential election is also significant because low or high participation is an important signal and indicator of the running of the democratic process and the embodiment of people's sovereignty."

The decision and activity of a person or group of people to actively involved in political life by choosing one of the Presidential, Vice-Presidential, and Legislative Candidates. The vision-mission element in its work program is more dominantly elected in 19 (nineteen) Districts in 5 (five) Electoral Districts than the figure factor when using four indicators. The choosing of constituents for the presidential election and parliamentary elections in Sambas Regency's five electoral districts is also heavily influenced by political figures and party influences. To determine the continuation of the next five years in overseeing and monitoring development and directly or indirectly influencing pro-people policies, 'public policy. Conventionally, this activity includes actions such as: voting in the presidential election a few months ago, precisely on April 17, 2019. The influence of the relationship between voters with one of the Presidential and Vice-Presidential and Legislative Candidates is also marked by several factors, such as the results of interviews with religious leaders in Sambas Regency with the initials HH, as follows:

"In my opinion, the dominant factor of voters in the presidential election. Legislative elections are influenced by the figure itself carried by political parties, which, of course, the value of trust, the value of struggle, togetherness in society has been tested. A Presidential and Vice-Presidential Candidate and a Legislative Candidate have good behavior in society, and he can convince the public as voters to vote for him. So that if the work program of the candidates for President and Vice President and Legislative Candidates submitted by the candidates themselves directly comes to Sambas Regency, it will have a considerable impact. Besides being continued by the success team itself, it helps influence constituents' thoughts and final decisions to choose them."

Likewise, political parties are also influential, although, in my opinion, the factors of Presidential and Deputy Candidates and figure candidates are compared to political parties and the highest legislative elections

that can determine the choices of the people of Sambas Regency. The author has explored from the research journey in several locations in Sambas Regency that the provisional conclusion regarding political issues in the 2019 presidential and parliamentary elections is not an exaggeration to say that the influence of border development can determine people's choices. Of course, explaining the visions and missions that are packaged in the framework of the work program for the next five years will affect the eyes of the people of Sambas Regency.

The presidential election (presidential election) and the 2019 legislative election were the loudest and most exciting. This can be seen in the campaigns carried out by the two pairs of candidates using social media. Of course, it also brings influence to the Sambas Regency area. In the 2019 presidential election and legislative election, the battle still looks conventional in campaigning. So, in the 2019 presidential election and legislative election, the campaign is more modern by using social media as a media tool to convey the vision and mission within the framework of the work program for the 2019 term of office. Until 2024. The tools used by pairs of candidates for the presidential election and legislative elections through social media are not only campaign tools to publish the vision, mission, programs.

Social media is not too much in the 2019 presidential and legislative elections; social media has become a separate force for political campaigns used by both pairs of candidates and legislative candidates who reach Sambas Regency. To study and explain that the 2019 presidential and legislative elections in Sambas Regency have led to election disputes. For this reason, the legal apparatus is obliged to act reasonably to resolve the commotion throughout Indonesia in general and in the Sambas Regency area. "One factor in the dispute between the 2019 presidential election and the legislative election, one of which is that each of them is still suspicious of the election results, accusing each other and making noise, making people in the regions as voters confused. Which is considered much cheating. It is not necessarily cheating, however.

Then the campaign period that is too long is also a factor in the dispute over the presidential and 2019 legislative elections. Because the two pairs of candidates and the legislative candidates are equally tired and eventually lead to campaigns that are not substantive, attack each other and slander, and bring down. "Even the potential for conflict exists. It happens because of the polarization of the two camps who are still emotional, not rational. Conflicts can be created by one of the losing factions, or irresponsible people can do them. Plus, the emergence of fake news, "black campaigns," "rice pack troops," or "buzzers," Indonesian politicians, political parties, and their supporting organizations have built very aggressive discourses in the digital public sphere. The Indonesian middle class remembers the repercussions of the squabbles that led their family members or colleagues out of WhatsApp groups. Some people cannot even talk openly about whom they will vote for fear of causing divisions in the religious circle. The media that candidates widely use for the presidential and legislative elections is print media such as the Pontianak Post newspaper, Tribune, billboard print media, liplet prints, and banners displayed along the way to make research more accessible.

In implementing the 2019 presidential and legislative elections, both Prabowo and Jokowi and legislative candidates have buzzer teams tasked with creating discourse, counteracting – or even producing – "black campaign" materials in cyberspace. War terms are often used to describe today's digital public sphere. Indonesia is said to have experienced a period when "online soldiers" and "cyber soldiers" were "armed." No wonder several Indonesians have described the current situation as a "hoax emergency." Jokowi also mentioned the dangers of "Russian propaganda." "They do not care if it will cause division in society, disturb the peace, disturb the public," Jokowi said, describing propaganda as a systematic push to "spread slander, lies,

Experts have warned that social media can easily trigger conflict because of low literacy levels, reflecting on some extraordinary cases. According to academic Adi Prayitno, "Many people are still irrational and tend to be emotional when faced with different political views," which then makes them think politics is "a road to heaven or a battle between good and evil. Instead of creating conditions of "hoax emergency.", "most of the people who are busy fighting each other are cyber troops from both camps. Meanwhile, young people are increasingly avoiding the increasingly intelligent political discourse, especially on Twitter and Facebook, thus turning to apolitical platforms such as Instagram. Arise not because society wants better candidates,

Given these changes, it is no surprise that media economics has become one of economics' hottest subfields, with significant implications for political communication. Consumer political inclinations are used to segment the market [6]. The creation of news content for specific customer segments can be planned based on anticipated future demand [7]. Media competition's impact on policy results can have an impact on political communication[8]. Political communication that uses a regular and continuous rhythm will make it easier to be accepted by the community as an effort to win strategies in matches in the Sambas Regency area.

Democratic contests such as legislative elections, even though political parties carry out the candidates, are more individual. So, each individual must master good political communication and be awakened as early as possible before the match starts in a democratic party such as legislative elections. Every political party is built on a particular political ideology. The political ideology of a party, known as "party principles," is usually listed on the platform or manifesto of a political party, which contains elements of ideas, beliefs, values, and the party's view of life. Inevitably, political life is constantly developing in the people of Sambas Regency. Based on the flow of political thought has been taken for granted in the life of the people in Sambas Regency.

The team has also conducted interviews with political parties participating in the legislative elections in Sambas Regency, the importance of political communication with all communities, as stated by one of the Chairpersons of the Golkar Political Party with the initials AR who stated:

"Each contestant tries to establish political communication so that it is easily accepted by the community as voters so that they become the best in the eyes of the people; this fact further increases the competition that exists between contestants who are involved in democratic elections. In terms of implementing political communication as a political strategy to win the political competition, it is an important topic that must be discussed within political parties internally. Political communication is a strategy to win the competition; of course, it must be developed and implemented by the standards and provisions of the applicable rules to win the 2019 legislative election in Sambas Regency".

From the interviews above, it is clear that political communication for legislative candidates promoted by political parties needs to put the context of "competition" in the political system. The more transparent political activities and communication and the public's desire for healthy politics have made the political system competitive apart from all manipulation and exploitation. The competition system needs to be seen in a dynamic context (dynamic, competition). In dynamic competition, it should be realized that a political party does not exist alone; some political opponents also have the same goal of being elected as The Regional People's Representative Assemblymembers in the Sambas Regency.

Political communication and the role of supporting political parties have provided political education. They are aware of supporting the legislative elections, as the results of interviews with religious leaders HB stated as follows:

"Political communication in today's society has received political education from political parties which are relatively wider and better than the previous society. In previous eras, political communication has increasingly understood (understand) about politics with all its gait and stripes. Political communication can be built through formal education to provide great services for increasing public awareness in various fields of life, including coming to polling stations to elect one legislative candidate to develop his area according to his electoral district".

From the discussions and interviews mentioned above, it is clear that political communication is an essential tool as a winning strategy for legislative candidates in 19 (Nineteen) Districts divided by General Election Commissions into 5 (five) electoral districts. Political communication is built not only to commercialize people's lives but to know the structure of society. In the past, people saw that politics was something noble and high. Now they see it more pragmatically. Society is faced with increasingly high demands for life amid global competition that has changed the character of society to become more pragmatic. People are increasingly reluctant to discuss ideological issues, which is the center of discussion and debate about the actual problems. So that with intense political communication to voters by legislative candidates, there will be opportunities for victory, and of

course, they will be elected as members of the The Regional People's Representative Assembly of Sambas Regency.

Voter's Knowledge of the Vision and Mission of the Legislative Candidate's Work Program. The study and discussion of research results on voter knowledge of the vision and mission in the work program of each legislative candidate are very much needed by the community as voters in Sambas Regency. Products in political marketing talk about how political parties, legislative candidates, and successful teams from political parties are presented to constituents. This product contains concepts, vision missions, and work programs. Implementing this participatory policy and deliberation supports the state government to be independent and active because the community controls the balance of regional development from the planning stage in the election of legislative candidates (Elyta, Zulkarnaen, & Herlan, 2020). Of course, with the methods of each legislative candidate during the campaign.

To gain voters' knowledge of legislative candidates, it can be seen from each political party that sent them to General Election Commission of Sambas Regency, based on their respective electoral areas. What are the issues that political parties spread to the public as voters? Such as the products of the vision and mission and work programs of each political party. According to National standards, the Research Team cites two political parties, Gerindra and PAN, in Sambas Regency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Political communication is the political capital for the election of the President and Legislature in Sambas Regency. The main target is the people in Sambas Regency. They had successfully carried out the Presidential and Legislative elections on April 17, 2019. Of course, the focus and hope of all people is synchronization in implementing the wheels of government, namely the Government Region (Executive) and another set with an elected Legislature. The voter's decision to give birth to regional leaders as their representatives in The Regional People's Representative Assembly of Sambas Regency is full of hope. Of course, it cannot be separated from the hard work of all leadership elements. The figure factors of legislative candidates and political parties as political vehicles and vision-missions and work programs are critical for the next 5 (five) years. Moreover, the typology of voters and the relationship between the work program and the typology of voters in the presidential and legislative elections, the development that will be carried out, so to achieve the development goals according to the intended vision, a public policy strategy is needed. The primary policy strategy is to overcome internal and external problems by optimizing the potential of available natural and human resources by taking advantage of existing opportunities and overcoming challenges by tackling problems faced in regional development in Sambas Regency.

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